

Deliverable

D7.3 List of Events

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1. Introduction

PRO-Ethics' overall objective is to create a comprehensive, co-developed, tested, and widely consulted Ethics Framework that enables a more effective handling of the ethical dimensions of innovation, with a special focus on the engagement of non-traditional stakeholders in participative innovation, to the benefit of more relevant, fair and effective innovation activities. The events planned in the course of the project are tailored to this objective, covering all steps necessary to ensure both the highest quality standard and maximum uptake of the core outputs of PRO-Ethics, with the highest possible benefit to the end-users of the PRO-Ethics Framework and Practical Guidelines.

To facilitate communication, General Assembly Meetings with representatives of all project partners are planned in regular intervals. To these meetings, members of the PRO-Ethics advisory board are invited to join either in person or online, lending their expertise each step along the process.

PRO-Ethics is anchored around real life experiments in the context of 11 pilots – research and innovation activities that engage non-traditional stakeholders implemented by the participating research funding organisations (RFOs). These pilots are divided into the 4 already running Pilots Phase I, and 7 to be developed in Pilots Phase II. Through analysis, comparison, and reflection of the Pilots Phase I, a first framework for reporting and assessing is co-developed, which in turn serves as a basis to create and test the Pilots Phase II. This whole process is facilitated by **3 cross-pilot learning workshops** at different stages of the project. The creation of the Pilots Phase II is the sole focus of a **co-creation workshop**, followed by a **training for ethical engagement processes** to support the partnering RFOs in implementing the new Pilots.

Meanwhile, to ensure both high engagement, comprehensive uptake, as well as the consideration of outside perspectives, **3 stakeholder engagement workshops** and **2 dialogue workshops with ethics bodies** are held in parallel to these workshops, often back-to-back with other events. In the first year of the project, an additional **workshop with ethics bodies** is held in context of a EUREKA case study to reflect on PRO-Ethics' themes.

Finally, in each of the eight RFO partner countries, one **national (or regional) take-up conference** will be organised in PRO-Ethics final year. The events are aimed at national policy audiences to influence wider national ecosystems towards ethical citizen engagement. Specific target groups will be policy makers, ethics committees, municipalities, and clients of RFOs. PRO-Ethics' **final international conference** will highlight the importance of an ethical baseline concerning citizens involvement, inform about project results and demonstrate achievements to core stakeholders in Europe and beyond (RFOs, European Commission, national policymakers, industry, citizens and CSOs, ethics bodies etc.). It aims to establish commitment to ethical citizen engagement and wide uptake of PRO-Ethics Framework and Practical Guidelines.

In light of COVID-19, some of these events have to be adapted for an online format, which means both scope and methodology might have to be adjusted accordingly. This is an ongoing process, although a number of upcoming workshops have already been moved online: The first cross-learning workshop planned for Oslo in M6, the first dialogue with ethics committees and the EUREKA workshop with ethics bodies planned for Brussels in M9, and the workshop for the selection of IT tools planned for Berlin in M10. The responsible partners for each of these events are reviewing available technologies and methodologies to achieve the goals of each event. Finally, as the second cross-learning workshop was already planned to be held online, it is a possibility to switch the location of the first two workshops, holding the second one physically in Oslo. While this is not yet decided, the situation remains in close observation, with the consortium committed to adapting to the changing needs, ensuring the highest quality outcomes of the workshops and, in the end, the project.

Below is a list of the most important meetings, and the timeframe for which they are planned.

2. List of Events

List of PRO-Ethics Events					
Time	Place	Event Type	Event Content	Target Group	Responsible Partner
M1/Jan20	Vienna	General Assembly Meeting		Consortium partners	ZSI
M6/Jun20	Oslo/online	1 st Cross-learning Workshop	RFOs follow, reflect on, learn from, challenge, and inspire each other to advance towards the goals of their pilots. Exchange of ethics practices in the pilots of Phase I.	RFO partners	DBT
M9/Sep20	Brussels/online	1 st Dialogue with ethics committees and research integrity bodies	Encourage and intensify the dialogue between policy makers, funding agencies, and ethics and research integrity bodies. Integrate the expectations of ethics and research integrity bodies into the project and especially the Pilots.	EUREKA Ethics Panel, TAFTIE, ALLEA, EUREC Office, ENRIO, ECs Research Integrity Unit, etc.	Nesta
M9/Sep20	Brussels/online	Workshop with ethics bodies	General reflection on ethics of innovation, barriers in implementation and delivery of ethics requirements, differences between theory and practice of implementation of ethics.	Project Officers, ethics experts, and beneficiaries	EUREKA
M10/Oct20	Berlin/online	IT Tool selection Workshop	Assess and rate which tools are most useful to RFOs, and which ones are most likely to be used in RFO engagement processes.	RFO partners	VDI/VDE-IT
M12/Dec20	Prague	General Assembly Meeting		Consortium partners	TACR+ZSI
M13/Jan21	Vienna	1 st Stakeholder Engagement Workshop	Presenting the draft ethics framework, monitoring and evaluation framework, pilot stories.	~15 external stakeholders (civil society, industry, ethics bodies, policy makers, external RFOs)	Nesta
M16/Apr21	Vienna	Co-Creation Workshop (right before 2 nd Stakeholder Engagement WS)	Develop the Pilots II by taking the ethics framework into account. Work on an ethics implementation strategy.	RFO partners	ZSI
M16/Apr21	Vienna	2 nd Stakeholder Engagement Workshop (right after Co-Creation WS)	Critically review ethical aspects (including shortcomings and pitfalls) within the Pilot II plans developed by RFOs the day before.	~15 external stakeholders (civil society, industry, ethics bodies, policy makers, external RFOs)	Nesta
M19/Jul21	Vienna	Training for ethical engagement processes	Empower participating RFOs to properly prepare Pilots II and achieve the best possible effects of the draft ethics framework.	RFO partners	EUREC Office
M24/Dec21	Berlin	General Assembly Meeting		Consortium partners	VDI/VDE-IT+ZSI
M28/Apr22	Online/Oslo	2 nd Cross-learning Workshop	Exchange of ethics practices in the pilots of Phase II.	RFO partners	DBT

Time	Place	Event Type	Event Content	Target Group	Responsible Partner
M36/Dec22	Brussels	General Assembly Meeting		Consortium partners	Innoviris+ZSI
M36/Dec22	Brussels	2 nd Dialogue with ethics committees and research integrity bodies	Discussion on how PRO-Ethics can practically support the work of ethics committees and research integrity bodies in view of new interaction modes in R&I projects	Broader audience of national and regional actors	Nesta
M39/Mar23	Copenhagen	3 rd Cross-learning Workshop (right before 3 rd Stakeholder Engagement WS)	Taking up the practical learnings of the RFOs for finalizing and fine-tuning the PRO-Ethics framework.	RFO partners, TUD, Sciences Po	DBT
M39/Mar23	Copenhagen	3 rd Stakeholder Engagement Workshop (right after 3 rd Cross-learning WS)	Focus on lessons learned in the implementation of the draft ethics framework in the real-life pilots in phase II.	~15 external stakeholders (civil society, industry, ethics bodies, policy makers, external RFOs)	Nesta
M37-M40 Jan23-Apr23		8 national take-up conferences (in 8 RFO partner countries)	Learn how innovation activities can be enhanced by ethically sound engagement processes targeting non-traditional stakeholders.	RFOs, civil society, researchers, industry, ethics bodies, policy makers and regional authorities	All RFO partners
M45/Sep23	Delft	General Assembly Meeting		Consortium partners	TUD+ZSI
M46/Oct23	Brussels	Final Conference	Identify and discuss inspiring practices and use cases to increase open innovation processes with the help of the PRO-Ethics framework.	All stakeholders	RCN

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